

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. JANETH L. LACOSTALES

Instructor I

Cebu Technological University – Barili Campus

janeth.lacostales@ctu.edu.ph

“OBSESSION”

Zero views. Lou sadly stared at her laptop. It has been a year since she started this YouTube journey but up to this very moment, she still couldn't gain any views. She has researched well about how the algorithm works and made sure she had applied every strategy to make her content known but nothing worked. If only she hadn't quit her job and decided to be a full-time content creator, her life wouldn't have been this miserable. She already felt so pathetic creating videos nobody even watches. She needs to create a content that would go viral.

After pausing for some time, an idea came to mind, fake news, controversies, and issues. Those things would create a buzz. So, she gathered photos and videos about a rising star. Then, she also gathered photos and videos about a veteran actress. Now, she is one hundred percent sure that this story will go viral with proper editing skills and a good storyline. That night, Lou did not even think of sleeping. Her story will surely blow up, subscribers and views will also blow up, she can smell money.

At last, all the editing was done perfectly, no one would even think it is fake news. In her video, she made it appear like the rising star and the veteran actress were dating after a project that they did together. Confident and excited, she then uploaded the video on YouTube. Truly, in just two minutes, views rose up to one thousand and it kept rising by a thousand view per minute! Surely, her video blew up! Hence, she decided to make more, thinking that if she makes that story more exciting, she will gain more too. And just like that, her subscribers grew from zero to fifty thousand in just a week. But she is hungry for more. She carefully created more and more videos about those two famous individuals, playing with every viewer's mind. In turn, she finally got monetized and earned a huge sum of money from her content. However, just when income started to enter steadily, she received an email. It says,

“Hi! I am Lady Xantelle's manager from BCD Entertainment, I've found out that you are the owner of the YouTube Channel, “Bitesy Stories”. I hope you are well aware that the stories that you are posting in your channel are all false. We ask you to please take down your channel and all your videos at once, otherwise, we will be forced to file a case against you.”

Respectfully,

Mike Moody

Manager

BCD Entertainment

Lou froze at one moment, “How did they find out when I posted everything anonymously?”

She knew, she had to make a move, unless she wanted to go broke again. So, Lou immediately deleted her channel, and made a new one while smiling an evil smile, staring at her laptop. She said, "This time, I will make sure I won't be caught."

With the same tactic, she made her videos blow up again. She even doubled her earning this time because she made sure to upload to every social media platform. She thought, it would be a total waste if she just leaves a good storyline behind. But she knew, she could be caught so, she went hiding before the police gets a chance to track her down. She knew she will surely go to jail if she gets caught so, she made sure everything is settled and money flow is never interrupted while she goes hiding. Her hunger for money and obsession to fame grew even deeper. She is now willing to destroy every person that stands in her way.

Although Lou thinks she is unstoppable, tables began to turn around one day. When she went out to run her daily errands, the detective who has been trying to catch her, identified her. It surely was a long chase but Lou was sneaky, so she escaped the detective's eyes. In her hideout, Lou started to panic, she doesn't want to go to jail but she also doesn't want to lose her way of living. She figured; she hasn't saved up more for her sibling's education. She is the breadwinner of their family. Who will take care of the family's expenses if she goes to jail? She had better keep her distance to the public. She thought, her hands were already dirty, thus, needs to play even dirtier this time.

With one click, she planted an issue about the detective who was trying to catch her, and in just a month, that same detective was relieved of his office. "Success!" she thought. Now, she has gotten rid of the eye that keeps looking for her. But she was wrong. Although the detective got fired, he desperately continued to look for Lou. Alas! The detective found out where Lou's hideout is, called his colleagues, and lead the raid. Police officers came, surrounding her hideout. Lou doesn't have a clue how to escape this time so, she hurried to the kitchen, took the knife, and went out of the house. She looked at the numerous guns pointing at her and smiled, saying, "What is this? Am I some kind of a gangster that you needed to surround me with all these guns? Come on, I am just a content creator trying to create a buzz in the internet! Couldn't you just give me a chance?"

The detective replied, "You were already given a chance. Do you remember how the manager of the BCD Entertainment reached out to you? They could've given you a better way of living. After all, you're still too young to be caught up in this. You can choose to surrender. There is a better life after this."

Lou scoffed, "Surrender, are you kidding me? Just when money is now constantly flowing, you're asking me to surrender? I'd rather die, man!"

Then Lou slit her own throat with the knife in her hands, blood thrusting everywhere. "I have worked so hard to get what I wanted. I am not letting go of it. I'd rather die with it." Lou said, as she was panting, gasping for breath.

Thankfully, the cut wasn't that deep, Lou remained alive. Later, she opened her eyes and found herself in the hospital bed. Sitting at her bedside was her mother. "Ma? What are you doing here? Why am I still alive?"

"Lou," her mother said. "I never imagined you'd reach this point. Remember the many times I've told you? I am content even though we are poor. We can make it through if we just help each other. This isn't what I imagined for us. But what has been done is already done. You need to learn from your mistakes."

Lou replied, "Ma, I'm sorry. I just thought money would make me happy but no, it made me greedy, it made me obsessed," she continued, "If I weren't meant to die, then maybe, I was meant to go to jail. I have nowhere to go now. After all, I am guilty of doing all these crimes of maliciously shaming people online, making up fake stories about them. This is what I deserve."

Lou dela Peña was sentenced to twelve years in prison for violating the Cybercrime Prevention Act (RA 10175).

